

A Study on Work Life Balance Amongst Software Employees Post Covid

Dr. B. Swathi¹, Mohammed Ismaieel Shaik Hyder², Hamza Shariff³

¹*Head, Research and Consultancy Assistant Professor of Commerce St. Mary's College*

²*Undergraduate Student Bachelor of Commerce (General) St. Mary's College*

³*Undergraduate Student Bachelor of Commerce (General) St. Mary's College*

Abstract - The work life balance of software employees post covid-19 pandemic has altered the work environment significantly. The review of literature examines how work life balance has evolved in the post pandemic era, mostly focusing on the software development profession, such as remote work adaptation, extended screen time and high demand of cognitive mind. The shift of hybrid to fully remote work has resulted in greater flexibility but also broken the boundaries between professional and personal life. This shift has given rights to new challenges such as disrupted routines, difficulty disconnecting from work, and increased burnout.

The study aims to explore the key factors that influence work life balance which includes technological advancements, individual coping strategies, and practices of team collaboration. The research also assesses how organizational policies impact on building sustainable work environments, such as mental health support, productivity driven outcomes, and flexible schedules. The data was gathered through case studies evolving software employees across regions and organizational context. The findings from the research indicate that employees who have established clear boundaries, prioritize mental wellbeing, and leverage productivity tools reported improve work life balance. Conversely, insufficient support from the organization and the over dependency on digital communication tools contributed to increase in work related stress. The research concludes with recommendations for both employees and employers to navigate through post covid-19 work environment and emphasizing the importance to maintain a healthy balance between professional and personal life.

Key Words: work life balance, post covid-19, remote work, post pandemic era, burnout, mental health support, software employees, hybrid work.

INTRODUCTION

Work-life balance is the practice of prioritizing personal and professional commitments in a way that ensures neither aspect dominates the other. It involves managing time, energy, and responsibilities effectively to create a healthy equilibrium between work demands and personal needs, such as family, leisure, health, and self-care. A balanced life can enhance productivity, reduce stress, and improve overall well-being.

Work life balance is a modern abbreviation for striking a balance between career and personal goals. The term work life balance was first used in 1986 although work life balance programs have been around since the 1930's. Before World War II, W. K. Kellogg company replaced the traditional method of calling employees for a 3-day 8-hour shift to 4-day 6-hour shift which increased employees' morale and productivity.

Coronavirus has given rise to different types of diseases around the world. The virus started in China in 2019 and has expanded to other countries. The virus had a heavy effect on humans particularly the respiratory system. Due to this pandemic the life and routine of software employees has been altered. Due to the availability of technology accessible from anywhere helps the connectivity of people as delineated the boundaries between career life and personal life. In this competitive era organizations are striving hard to help the employees who are facing a lot of issues with balancing the personal and professional lives due to various reasons. One of the major reasons employees are facing imbalance is due to heavy competition and a stressed work environment which results in poor performance. All the factors above can have a snowball effect on software employees as they try to balance these factors and challenges at work and fall behind trying to do so. Software employees have a high risk of suffering from burn out due to the stressed environment. Burn out if left unattended can lead employees to alienation from work related activities to the point employees feel numb from the work. Burnout also leads to emotional exhaustion due to which employees feel emotionally drained and unable to cope with challenges in their personal lives.

Review of literature

Covid-19 pandemic significantly impacted software employees work life balance with introducing remote work alongside both benefits and challenges. The study indicated that while the employees experienced increased flexibility, they also faced difficulties in maintaining boundaries between work and personal life which led to potential burn out and decrease job satisfaction. Research has shown a negative correlation between burnout and job satisfaction and a weak positive relation between work life balance and job satisfaction among software employees. Overall, the shift to remote work has resulted in a huge impact on employees' productivity and wellbeing. (Michel Zaitouni et al, 2024)

Research conducted to assess the relationship of job satisfaction, work-life balance, and burnout of software employees aimed to identify the differences between gender and work models such as work from home, work from office and hybrid arrangements. The findings showed moderate negative correlation between job satisfaction and burnout, indicating high level of burnouts among software employees associated with lower level of job satisfaction. Additionally, there was a weak correlation between work-life balance and job satisfaction, suggesting higher job satisfaction is related to better work-life balance. The study also concluded that there is no difference between burnout, work-life balance, or job satisfaction based on gender or different work models. (John Thomson et al, 2023). Work-life balance plays a crucial role in organizing better productivity among employees. A healthy blend of employee's work and personal life results in positive influence on their wellbeing. (Magdalene et al, 2020)

The shift from office spaces to virtual work environments has brought significant changes to software employees' work-life balance, particularly in Sri Lanka. Understanding the key factors that influence this balance during remote work is essential, as limited research has explored this area. Supervisor support and trust, along with having a dedicated workspace, play a crucial role in maintaining a healthy balance between professional and personal life. Interestingly, factors such as working conditions, access to the organizational network, and the number of children do not appear to have a significant impact. By analyzing data using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling, it becomes evident that fostering a supportive work culture and ensuring employees have a suitable home workspace can enhance overall well-being in remote work settings. (Ranitha Weerathna et al, 2022)

Work-life balance and commuting challenges present significant conflicts, particularly in dual-career households in the UK. Professional work-group cultures can influence and sometimes limit the effectiveness of work-life balance policies, making it difficult for employees to separate work and personal life. The extent of spillover between work and non-work activities is further shaped by commuting preferences, adding another layer of complexity. In regions like Greater Nottingham, a major employment hub in England's East Midlands, commuting patterns and workplace cultures play a crucial role in shaping the work-life balance of software employees. Work-group cultures often act as barriers, particularly for women, preventing them from achieving a satisfactory balance between career and personal life. This issue highlights the need to reassess flexible work arrangements to ensure they do not negatively impact the careers of highly skilled workers, especially working mothers. Addressing these concerns can help HR managers and employees develop effective work-life balance policies that consider commuting challenges and support dual-career households. (Wheatley D, 2012)

The post-pandemic era has brought significant changes to work-life balance and its impact on employee performance.

Over the past five years, organizational practices and trends have evolved, particularly with the adoption of flexible work arrangements. Remote work and hybrid models have redefined the balance between professional and personal life, influencing employee well-being and productivity. The shift away from traditional work structures has had both positive and negative effects, with some employees benefiting from increased flexibility while others face challenges in maintaining clear boundaries between work and personal responsibilities. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for organizations aiming to implement effective policies that enhance work-life balance and overall job performance. (Daniel Koech et al, 2024)

The COVID-19 pandemic brought significant challenges to maintaining work-life balance, directly impacting employee satisfaction, motivation, and retention. The equilibrium or disequilibrium between professional and personal life during this period played a crucial role in shaping employees' overall well-being and job attitudes. An empirical analysis of employees' experiences during the pandemic highlights the strong correlation between work-life balance and key workplace outcomes. Surveys reveal that a well-balanced work-life dynamic leads to higher job satisfaction, improved performance, and lower turnover intentions. Conversely, imbalance results in dissatisfaction, reduced motivation, and an increased likelihood of employees leaving their organizations. These findings emphasize the need for companies to implement policies that promote a healthier work-life balance, particularly during times of crisis, to maintain a motivated and stable workforce. (nca Antoaneta Varzaru et al, 2023)

Remote work during the COVID-19 pandemic presented both anticipated benefits and unexpected challenges for employees' work-life balance. While flexibility and family-friendly arrangements were initially seen as advantages, many employees struggled with blurred boundaries between work and personal life. A thematic analysis of empirical studies from March 2020 to August 2021 highlights the gap between expectations and reality in remote work settings. Challenges such as increased workload, lack of ergonomic support, and difficulties in maintaining work-life separation emerged as key concerns. However, strategies like setting clear boundaries, providing ergonomic support, and offering training can help mitigate these challenges. By addressing these issues, organizations can create more sustainable remote work environments that genuinely support employees' well-being and productivity. (Shirmohammadi et al, 2022)

The shift to remote work during the COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the work-life balance of both male and female employees, with notable differences between the two groups. A comparative analysis reveals that women experienced a heavier workload than men due to their increased personal involvement in their jobs while working from home. However, there were no significant gender differences in how work interruptions affected personal life. The study highlights the role of organizational support in reducing work-life conflicts, emphasizing that companies can

help alleviate work interference with personal responsibilities. By implementing supportive policies, organizations can contribute to a more balanced and sustainable work environment, particularly for women facing greater challenges in remote work settings. (Rabuni Aiswarya et al, 2023)

Objective and Methodology

The main objective of this study is to explore how post COVID-19 work environments have affected the work-life balance of software employees. Due to pandemic many major changes were brought to workplace dynamics such as making digital collaboration tools essential for business continuity. While it improved flexibility, it also introduced challenges like team cohesion and work-life balance, leading to the rise of hybrid work models. Companies adapted different types of work models such as work from office, remote work or hybrid, each with different levels of job satisfaction, difference in productivity and wellbeing in different ways. This review looks at the challenges faced by software employees, such as longer working hours, difficulty logging out from work and digital burnout. At the same time, the research also highlights benefits like more flexibility, improved collaboration opportunities and better autonomy. This study relies on a review of existing literature, industry reports and research articles that examine work-life balance, post COVID workplace trends and remote work. The data for the study was gathered from several secondary and published sources like business reports, surveys conducted by organizations, and academic papers.

SCOPE

The scope of this study is to focus on software employees across various locations and industries, as their profession is well suited for hybrid/remote work. The study examined how different work models such as hybrid, remote, and in-office affect software employees in their daily routine, responsibilities and personal wellbeing. Key factors considered were workload, stress levels of employees, mental health concerns of employees and communication challenges. The study was conducted over a research period from 2021 to current analyzing the impact of remote work on workplace dynamics. It examined changes in work-life balance, productivity, and organizational strategies during and after the pandemic.

CONCLUSIONS

Work-life balance in software companies has become increasingly complex due to the rise of technology, which has blurred the boundaries between professional and personal life. With the widespread use of mobile devices and email, employees often find it difficult to disconnect from work,

leading to challenges in maintaining a healthy balance. This issue is particularly relevant for working mothers, mature employees, and minority groups, who may face additional pressures in balancing their responsibilities. Organizational support plays a crucial role in helping employees manage these challenges by fostering a culture that prioritizes work-life balance. Implementing welfare measures and supportive policies can enhance employee satisfaction and productivity, making it essential for companies to integrate work-life balance strategies into their corporate framework. (Dr Shankar et al, 2017)

The COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted work-life balance, particularly among software workers. The sudden shift to remote work blurred the lines between professional and personal life, leading to increased challenges in maintaining a healthy balance. Factors such as extended working hours, lack of clear boundaries, and increased workload have contributed to heightened stress and decreased well-being among employees. Moreover, the phenomenon of "technostress," arising from constant connectivity and the pressure to be perpetually available, has further exacerbated these challenges, compromising both work performance and personal life. Organizations play a crucial role in addressing these issues by implementing supportive policies that promote work-life balance. Strategies such as offering flexible working hours, encouraging regular breaks, and providing resources for mental health support can significantly enhance employee satisfaction and productivity. Additionally, fostering a culture that respects personal time and discourages overwork is essential in mitigating the negative impacts of remote work. By proactively addressing these challenges, companies can ensure a more balanced and sustainable work environment for their employees. (Abigail Marks et al, 2004)

The COVID-19 pandemic brought a sudden shift to remote work, significantly impacting software employees' productivity and overall work experience. A study conducted at Microsoft revealed a range of outcomes, with some employees benefiting from improved focus time and fewer workplace distractions, while others faced challenges that hindered efficiency. Difficulties such as inadequate home office setups, struggles with communication and collaboration, and the challenge of balancing work and personal responsibilities emerged as key concerns. While remote work allowed certain employees to maintain or even enhance their productivity, others experienced disruptions that affected their performance. These findings highlight the importance of understanding individual experiences and implementing targeted support strategies to ensure a balanced and productive remote work environment for software employees. (Denae Ford et al, 2021)

The COVID-19 pandemic led to an abrupt transition to remote work for software employees, raising concerns about its effects on their productivity, satisfaction, and overall well-being. A two-wave longitudinal study involving 192 software engineers examined how remote work influenced key aspects of their professional activities. While the amount of time spent on tasks such as coding, bug fixing, and assisting colleagues

remained largely consistent with pre-pandemic levels, employees reported a decline in both job satisfaction and productivity. One of the primary challenges was the reduced quality of communication, as remote collaboration often lacked the immediacy and efficiency of in-person interactions. Additionally, the blurring of work-life boundaries made it difficult for employees to disconnect, leading to increased stress and burnout. The findings emphasize the importance of organizational support in mitigating these issues, particularly by improving virtual communication strategies, fostering a healthy work-life balance, and providing resources to enhance remote work environments. Addressing these concerns can help sustain developer well-being and efficiency in long-term remote or hybrid work settings. (Daniel Russo et al, 2023)

The COVID-19 pandemic prompted leading Indian IT companies to adopt remote work strategies, such as Work-From-Home (WFH) and Work-From-Anywhere (WFA), to ensure employee safety while maintaining client deliverables. An exploratory sequential mixed-method study involving eight prominent IT firms in India revealed that these strategies led to minimal disruption in operations, largely due to the rapid deployment of technological tools facilitating the transition. Financial analyses indicated that these remote work approaches did not negatively impact company profitability or client satisfaction. Additionally, benefits such as reduced carbon footprints, improved work-life balance, and de-urbanization were observed. However, challenges emerged, including diminished team cohesiveness and concerns regarding employee emotional well-being. The study underscores the necessity for agile organizational planning to address unforeseen contingencies, ensuring both business continuity and employee welfare in evolving work environments. (Mythili kolluru, 2021)

The findings revealed that the work-life balance of software employees post COVID-19 has changed significantly with the introduction of remote and hybrid work models which gave software employees more flexibility, improved productivity and long commutes. However along with the benefits software employees had to face some challenges like setting work boundaries, increased burnout and longer working hours. Fully remote workers mostly struggle to separate between work life and personal life, while hybrid workers tend to have a better experience by combining in-person collaboration with flexibility. Software employees who are returning to offices have different opinions, while some of the software employees appreciate the work environment and other software employees find the work environment very stressful.

Organizations tend to have happier and productive employees when the factors such as setting clear policies, promotion of mental health and the encouragement of flexible work arrangement are provided to the employees. For software employees setting boundaries, management of workload effectively and prioritizing self-care are the main key components to avoid burnout. Organizations must have open communication with employees on workload and expectations.

In summary, while post COVID-19 work models offer independence and flexibility, work models are also required to

have careful management to ensure wellbeing of software employees. Both software employees and companies must work together in order to create a sustainable and balanced work environment.

REFERENCES

Balance on the Well Being of Employees at Quantum Software Solutions PVT LTD (2020). *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET)*, 11 (3), pp 120-127, 2020, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3565161>

Bocean, Claudiu George, Luminita Popescu, Anca Antoaneta Varzaru, Costin Daniel Avram, and Anica Iancu. 2023. "Work-Life Balance and Employee Satisfaction during COVID-19 Pandemic" *Sustainability* 15, no. 15: 11631. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su151511631>

Denae Ford, Margaret-Anne Storey, Thomas Zimmermann, Christian Bird, Sonia Jaffe, Chandra Maddila, Jenna L. Butler, Brian Houck, and Nachiappan Nagappan. 2021. A Tale of Two Cities: Software Employees Working from Home during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *ACM Trans. Softw. Eng. Methodol.* 31, 2, Article 27 (April 2022), 37 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3487567>

<http://dx.doi.org/10.2174/0118743501275173231023102400>

<https://doi.org/10.33565/MKSV.2024.01.01>

J., Deivasigamani & Shankar, Dr. (2017). Dimension of Work Life Balance in Software Companies. *Asian Journal of Applied Sciences.* 5. 10.24203/ajas.v5i2.4593.

Kolluru, Mythili & Krishnan, Kumutha & Kolluru, Shyam. (2021). Post COVID-19 Work Strategies and Implications: Insight on Indian it Sector. *ECONOMICS.* 9. 49-72. 10.2478/eoik-2021-0014.

Peter, Magdalene and Kavitha, Dr.S.Fabiyola, A Study on the Impact of Work Life

Russo D, Hanel PHP, Altnickel S, van Berkel N. Satisfaction and performance of software employees during enforced work from home in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Empir Softw Eng.* 2023;28(2):53. doi: 10.1007/s10664-023-10293-z. Epub 2023 Mar 9. PMID: 36915711; PMCID: PMC9996595.

Scholarios, Dora & Marks, Abigail. (2004). Work-life balance and the software worker. *Human Resource Management Journal.* 14. 54 - 74. 10.1111/j.1748-8583.2004.tb00119.x.

Shirmohammadi, M., Au, W. C., & Beigi, M. (2022). Remote work and work-life balance: Lessons learned from the covid-19 pandemic and suggestions for HRD practitioners. *Human Resource Development International,* 25(2), 163–181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13678868.2022.2047380>

Thomson, J. & Deepthi, DP (2023). Burnout, Work-Life Balance and Job Satisfaction Among Software Employees. *International Journal of Indian Psychology,* 11(2), 1102-1116. DIP:18.01.118.20231102, DOI:10.25215/1102.118

Weerarathna R, Rathnayake N, Yasara I, Jayasekara P, Ruwanpura D, Nambugoda S. Towards work-life balance or away? The impact

of work from home factors on work-life balance among software engineers during Covid-19 pandemic. PLoS One. 2022 Dec 14;17(12):e0277931. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0277931. PMID: 36516135; PMCID: PMC9750026.

[Wheatley, D.](#) (2012), "Work-life balance, travel-to-work, and the dual career household", [Personnel Review](#), Vol. 41 No. 6, pp. 813-831.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2024.e34084>